

OPORPH 2025: Book of Abstracts

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»ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES,
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND FOOD PRODUCTION«

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**Environmental resources, sustainable development
and food production – OPORPH 2025: Book of Abstracts**

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IMMOBILIZED HORSERADISH PEROXIDASE ON BIOMAGNETITE PARTICLES FOR EFFICIENT REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER

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Phenol is a highly toxic pollutant commonly found in industrial effluents, particularly from petrochemical, rubber, coal-processing, and dye industries, where its concentration can reach up to 185 mg/L. Enzymatic catalysis using peroxidases has been recognized as an environmentally friendly alternative for phenol removal, but its broader application is limited by enzyme instability and the inability to reuse free enzymes.

In this work, an innovative biocatalyst was developed by covalently immobilizing horseradish peroxidase onto biomagnetite particles synthesized in the presence of tangerine peel extract. The bioactive compounds incorporated during synthesis enhanced particle stability and functionalization, while glutaraldehyde served as a cross-linking agent for enzyme attachment. The resulting biocatalyst exhibited high catalytic activity (33.2 U/g at 30 °C, pH 6), retained over 60% activity across multiple reuse cycles, and maintained stability during 30 days of storage. Batch experiments using model phenol solutions (10 mg/L) demonstrated efficient removal, achieving 93% degradation within 60 minutes in the presence of hydrogen peroxide. Compared to the free enzyme, immobilized horseradish peroxidase provided higher removal efficiency, improved reusability, and greater operational stability. Due to its low-cost raw materials, simple preparation, and strong catalytic performance, the developed biocatalyst offers a promising solution for industrial wastewater treatment and regulation of phenol concentration in aquatic systems.

Keywords: immobilized peroxidase; tangerine peel extract; biomagnetite; phenol removal; wastewater treatment

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